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Abstract: This paper describes the details of the design of a small scale linear Fresnel reflector (SSLFR) applied to a daylighting system based on optical fiber bundles (OFBs). This study shows the influence of the design parameters of the SSLFR (mirror width, mirror length, reflector cavity height, and number of mirrors) and the parameters of the optical fiber. A new reflector cavity is designed, consisting of two right trapeziums. Each trapezium collects the incident solar irradiance of the mirrors located at each side of the central mirror. The reflector cavity has two focal points, located in the middle of the aperture of each trapezium. A MATLAB code was developed in order to obtain the optical efficiency of the new reflector cavity and numerical simulations are presented.

Two SSLFR configurations, C1 and C2, are studied. C1 is the configuration used in large-scale LFRs and does not consider the lateral movement of the OFBs, as it is the case in C2 configuration. Each of these configurations is analysed considering the optimal length and longitudinal position of the OFB. Numerical simulations are presented for both configurations using the MATLAB environment. Power consumption based calculations are carried out using the lumen method and the potential electric energy saving is evaluated. The results show a considerable electric energy saving with C2 configuration, although C1 configuration also presents good saving figures.

Highlights

- **First contribution: the design of a daylighting system based on OFB using a SSLFR.**
- **Second contribution: this work focuses on the design of a new reflector cavity.**
- **A daylighting system like this has not been studied in the literature so far.**
- **The cavity used in a conventional SSLFR is not suitable for this application.**
- **The work presented in this paper shows the luminous energy produced per month.**

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Development of a fiber daylighting system based on a small scale linear Fresnel reflector: Theoretical elements

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Abstract

This paper describes the details of the design of a small scale linear Fresnel reflector (*SSLFR*) applied to a daylighting system based on optical fiber bundles (*OFBs*). This study shows the influence of the design parameters of the *SSLFR* (mirror width, mirror length, reflector cavity height, and number of mirrors) and the parameters of the optical fiber. A new reflector cavity is designed, consisting of two right trapeziums. Each trapezium collects the incident solar irradiance of the mirrors located at each side of the central mirror. The reflector cavity has two focal points, located in the middle of the aperture of each trapezium. A MATLAB code was developed in order to obtain the optical efficiency of the new reflector cavity and numerical simulations are presented.

Two *SSLFR* configurations, C_1 and C_2 , are studied. C_1 is the configuration used in large-scale LFRs and does not consider the lateral movement of the OFBs, as it is the case in C_2 configuration. Each of these configurations is analysed considering the optimal length and longitudinal position of the OFB. Numerical simulations are presented for both configurations using the MATLAB environment. Power consumption based calculations are carried out using the lumen method and the potential electric energy saving is evaluated. The results show a considerable electric energy saving with C_2 configuration, although C_1 configuration also presents good saving figures.

Keywords:

Daylighting, Small scale Linear Fresnel Reflector, Optical fibers

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9 **1. Introduction**

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11 Over the last decade, global demand for artificial light has grown at an average rate of 2.4% per annum [1]. Annual growth was slower in IEA countries (1.8%) than in the rest of the world (3.6%). Globally, 133 petalumen-hours (Plmh) of electric light were consumed in 2005, an average of 20 megalumen-hours (Mlmh) of light per person, although light consumption is very unevenly distributed [1]. This growth in artificial light demand has caused that, over the last decade, the global electricity consumption for lighting applications has grown at 1.5% per annum, less than three-quarters of the light demand growth rate [1]. In the next 25 years, with the current socioeconomic trends and policies, the global electricity consumption for lighting is projected to rise to over 4250 TWh, which means an increase of 60% at an average rate of 1.9% per annum [1]. Different strategies have been proposed to reduce the energy consumption of lighting systems [2], [3].

28 Building lighting has been the subject of special attention, since lighting represents a high percentage of the energy consumed in buildings. It has been found that the main reason behind the increase of energy consumption is the rise of average illuminance level. The study of the use of daylighting systems to illuminate the interiors of buildings is not new [4]. Many later researchers have shown that it is possible to transfer sunlight into residential buildings, in order to complement artificial lighting [5], [6], [7]. The lighting electricity savings associated with the installation of daylighting systems in buildings is estimated to be around 50-80% [8].

39 In addition, many authors have studied the health benefits associated with the use of daylighting [9], [10], since illuminance amount and light quality are regarded as factors that define a healthy environment.

43 Daylighting systems are composed of five main elements [11]: sunlight sources, sunlight collection systems, sunlight transmission systems, lighting control systems, and solar luminaires. Sunlight collectors capture direct sunlight outside the building, sunlight distribution systems transmit sunlight to the interiors of the building, and solar luminaires distribute sunlight into the building.

51 There are three main types of sunlight collectors: parabolic dishes, parabolic troughs, and Fresnel lenses. A parabolic dish system consists of mirrors collected in the supporting structure to reflect and concentrate the solar radiation to the focus of the parabolic dish [12]. The parabolic dish is directed towards the sun automatically using a solar tracking mechanism, and the

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9 optical fiber is fixed permanently at the focus to collect reflected light [13],
10 [14]. In a parabolic trough system, a parabolic reflector plate is pointed at
11 the sun with a tracking control system [15], and the optical fiber is fixed
12 permanently at the focus of the parabolic concentrator to collect reflected
13 light [16]. Fresnel lens refract incident sunlight to a single focal point behind
14 the opposite side of the lens [17], where an optical fiber or a bundle of several
15 small fibers are mounted [18].
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18 Light transmission systems use several devices for transmitting sunlight
19 to the interiors of buildings: large-core optical fibers, optical fiber bundles
20 (OFBs), and hollow-core reflective lightpipes. The transmission of sunlight
21 via optical fiber is a flexible solution for daylighting systems and has some
22 advantages such as the exclusion of the ultraviolet and the more important
23 infrared parts. An individual optical fiber is a transparent and flexible fiber
24 with a diameter of the order of microns, consisting of a core and a clad. Core
25 diameters range from 7 microns to 1 mm. The fiber can be made of glass or
26 plastic. The plastic type provide more flexible solutions than the glass type,
27 though the attenuation is larger.
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30 The main objective of this work is to study the details of the design
31 of a small scale linear Fresnel reflector (*SSLFR*) applied to a daylighting
32 system based on optical fiber bundles (*OFBs*). This work has two novel
33 contributions. Firstly, the design of a daylighting system based on OFBs
34 using a SSLFR. To the best of our knowledge, a daylighting system with these
35 characteristics has not been studied in the literature so far. Some studies
36 have been published using parabolic dishes, parabolic troughs, and Fresnel
37 lenses as sunlight collectors, whereas this work evaluates the performance
38 of a SSLFR as the sunlight collector of a daylighting system. Secondly, this
39 work focuses on the design of a new reflector cavity, since the cavity used in a
40 conventional SSLFR is not suitable for this application. The work presented
41 in this paper shows the luminous energy produced per month by the proposed
42 daylighting system and an estimation of the electric energy saving in a typical
43 office room.
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49 The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the main com-
50 ponents of the daylighting system. Section 3 presents the parameters used
51 in the transversal and longitudinal studies, the design of the reflector cavity
52 and the calculation of the luminous flux of the daylighting system. Numerical
53 simulations are presented in Section 4 for different configurations of the
54 SSLFR. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main contributions and conclu-
55 sions of the paper.
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Nomenclature

A_{OFB}	Total <i>OFB</i> area (m^2)	n	Number of mirrors at each side of the central mirror
$A_{effec\ OFB\ i}$	Effective area of the <i>OFB</i> (m^2)	n_{core}	Refractive index of the core
BPF	Bundle packin fraction	n_{clad}	Refractive index of the clad
B	Lower side of the right trapeziums (m)	<i>OFB</i>	Optical fiber bundle
b	Less side of the right trapeziums (m)	Q_{OFB}	Total power on the <i>OFB</i> (W)
CI_m	Cleanliness factor of the mirror	$T(\lambda)$	Transmissivity
CI_{OFB}	Cleanliness factor of the <i>OFB</i>	W_M	Width of the mirrors (m)
CR	Concentration ratio	W_{ai}	Width illuminated on the aper- ture of the reflector cavity by the i -th mirror (m)
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiance (W/m^2)	W_{OFB}	Width of the <i>OFB</i> (m)
d	Separation between two consecu- tive mirrors (m)	α_i	Angle between the vertical at the focal point and the line connect- ing the center point of each mirror to the focal point ($^\circ$)
$dBloss$	Attenuation (dB/Km)	α_S	Height angle of the Sun ($^\circ$)
d_c	Individual optical fibre core diam- eter (m)	β_{OFB}	Angle between the <i>OFB</i> and the horizontal plane ($^\circ$)
d_{of}	Individual optical fibre diameter (m)	β_i	Tilt of $i - th$ mirror ($^\circ$)
f	Distance between the <i>OFB</i> and the mirrors (m)	β_M	Angle between the mirror axis and the horizontal plane ($^\circ$)
$G_{in,of}$	Input irradiance solar (W/m^2)	γ	Skew rays angle ($^\circ$)
$G_{out,of}$	Output irradiance solar (W/m^2)	γ_S	Azimuth of the sun ($^\circ$)
IAF	Incidence angle modifier	η_{opt}	Optical efficiency (%)
h	Depth of the air cavity (m)	η_{SL}	Solar luminaire efficiency (%)
K_b	Luminous efficacy (Lm/W)	θ_c	Acceptance angle ($^\circ$)
L	Length of the individual optical fiber (Km)	θ_{IA}	Inclination angle for residential roofing ($^\circ$)
L_M	Length of the mirrors (m)	θ_i	Angle between the normal to the mirror and the angle of incidence of the sun ($^\circ$)
L_{OFB}	Length of the <i>OFB</i> (m)	θ_L	Lateral incidence angle ($^\circ$)
L_{OFB}^l	Left length of the <i>OFB</i> (m)	θ_l	Longitudinal incidence angle ($^\circ$)
L_{OFB}^r	Right length of the <i>OFB</i> (m)	θ_t	Transversal incidence angle ($^\circ$)
l_{OFB}	Total illuminated length of the <i>OFB</i> (m)	θ_z	Zenith angle of the Sun ($^\circ$)
l_{OFB}^l	Left illuminated length of the <i>OFB</i> (m)	λ	Wavelength (nm)
l_{OFB}^r	Right illuminated length of the <i>OFB</i> (m)	μ	Angle between the reflected ray and the normal to the NS axis ($^\circ$)
L_i	Position of $i - th$ mirror ($0 \leq i \leq n$) (m)	ρ_m	Reflectivity of the primary mir- rors
N	Number of individual fibres	ρ_{rc}	Reflectivity of the reflector cavity
NA	Numerical aperture of the indi- vidual optical fiber	τ	Transmissivity of the glass

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2. Elements of the daylighting system

The main components of the proposed daylighting system are: sunlight source, SSLFR, OFBs, lighting control system, and solar luminaires. Fig.1 shows a schematic of the daylighting system proposed.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the daylighting system proposed.

2.1. Sunlight source

Sunlight is the primary light source for daylighting systems. The equation (1) is used to calculate the luminous efficacy of the direct radiation [19], defined as the ratio between the direct normal illuminance and the direct normal irradiance:

$$K_b = \frac{E_{bn}}{DNI} = \frac{K_m \cdot \int_{380}^{780} G_\lambda \cdot V_\lambda \cdot d\lambda}{\int G_\lambda \cdot d\lambda} \quad (1)$$

where E_{bn} is the direct normal illuminance (in lm/m^2 or lux), DNI is the direct normal irradiance (in W/m^2), K_m is the luminous efficacy constant for photopic vision, G_λ is the spectral irradiance, V_λ is the spectral sensitivity of the eye, and λ is the wavelength. V_λ is defined by the numerical values given in Table 1 of [20]. For monochromatic light with a wavelength of 555 nm, K_m has a value of 683 lm/W [20].

Several luminous efficacy models based on simultaneous illuminance and irradiance measurements have been developed [21]. Luminous efficacy can be expressed as a function of solar altitude [22], [23], [24]. Most researchers have proposed polynomial models of different degrees for calculating K_b [25], [26], [27]. According to Darula et al. [28], each region has its own constant of luminous efficacy.

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In this study we will use a technique which consists in the use of a single, averaged value of luminous efficacy [26]. An average value of K_b between 93 and 115 lm/W is suitable for beam luminous efficacy [29]. Munner [29] provides the accuracy evaluation of a luminous efficacy value of 104 lm/W.

2.2. SSLFR

A SSLFR has the configuration of a ‘conventional’ central LFR, and is composed of the following main elements: fixed structural system (1), mobile structural system (2), secondary reflector system (3), primary reflector system (4), mirror row (5), transmission means (7), and electric motors (8). The primary reflector system is composed of a row of mirrors arranged on a mobile frame. The secondary reflector system is located at a certain height from the primary reflector system and is composed of a reflector cavity in which the OFBs are located. This SSLFR has the possibility of three movements (see Fig. 2) as described in [30], [31]. Firstly, the mirrors can be rotated on the north-south axis, so as to follow the sun’s movement. Secondly, the mirror row can be rotated on the east-west axis. Finally, the receiver can also be rotated on the east-west axis. The possibility of longitudinal movement of the SSLFR is the main difference with the large-scale LFR. The most important parameters of this SSLFR are: mirror number, mirror width, mirror length, mirror separation, and vertical distance between the mirrors and the OFB. These parameters are related to the rest of the elements that form the daylighting system, as it will be analyzed in the following section.

Fig. 2. Computer visualisation of a SSLFR with three movements.

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9 *2.3. Optical fibre bundles*

10 An optical fibre bundle (OFB) is composed of tens to thousands of in-
11 dividual optical fibres, which are surrounded by epoxy glue as the filling.
12 Therefore, there are optical losses associated with each individual optical fi-
13 bre (attenuation and acceptance angle) and optical losses associated with the
14 bundles (scattered and absorbed in the epoxy glue).
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16 Theoretically, the attenuation of an individual optical fibre is dependent
17 on light wavelength and fibre length. The transmissivity of an individual
18 optical fibre is given by [32]:
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$$21 \quad T(\lambda) = \frac{G_{out,of}}{G_{in,of}} = 10^{\frac{-L \cdot dBloss}{10}} \quad (2)$$

22 where $T(\lambda)$ is the transmissivity for a specific wavelength (λ), $G_{out,of}$
23 is the output solar irradiance (W/m^2), $G_{in,of}$ is the input solar irradiance
24 (W/m^2), L is the fibre length (Km), and $dBloss$ is the attenuation at each
25 wavelength (dB/Km) or loss per kilometer. The individual optical fiber used
26 in this study has an attenuation of 12 dB/Km at 808 nm (manufacturer
27 data).
28

29 There are also losses associated with the incidence angle of sunlight in
30 the individual optical fiber. The total internal reflection depends on the
31 numerical aperture, which is given by [33]:
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$$33 \quad NA = \sin \theta_c = (n_{core}^2 - n_{clad}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

34 where NA is the numerical aperture, θ_c is the acceptance angle, n_{core}
35 is the refractive index of the core, and n_{clad} is the refractive index of the
36 clad. In theory, sunlight is transmitted efficiently if the incidence angles are
37 smaller than or equal to the acceptance angle. However, this affirmation is
38 not completely true due to the presence of intrinsic and extrinsic attenuation
39 losses [32]. The equation (3) is valid for meridional rays, which intersect the
40 axis of the individual optical fiber after each reflexión. Besides meridional
41 rays, there are also skew rays, which propagate by forming a spiral around
42 the individual optical fiber. Skew rays are three-dimensional rays, whereas
43 meridional rays propagate in a two-dimensional plane [33]. For skew rays the
44 numerical aperture is given by [33]:
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$$54 \quad NA = \sin \theta_c = \frac{(n_{core}^2 - n_{clad}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\cos \gamma} \quad (4)$$

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9 where γ is the reflection angle for skew rays within the individual optical
10 fiber. Since $\cos\gamma$ is < 1 , the acceptance angle is higher for skew rays. There-
11 fore, the expression for NA given in equation (3) for meridional rays is more
12 restrictive and, for this reason, we will consider all the sunlight as meridional
13 rays. Moreover, it is necessary to bear in mind the manufacturing process of
14 an individual optical fibre. This process is imperfect and as a result a small
15 fraction of sunlight is absorbed in the cladding [34].
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18 The sunlight will only be transmitted by the core area of every individual
19 optical fibre that forms the bundle. The sunlight that do not affect the core
20 area will be scattered in the cladding material or absorbed in the epoxy
21 material. The useful area of the bundle can be determined from the bundle
22 packing fraction (BPF) [35]:
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$$25 \quad BPF = \frac{N \cdot \pi \cdot d_c^2}{4 \cdot A_{OFB}} \quad (5)$$

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28 where N is the number of individual fibres, d_c is the fibre core diameter
29 and A_{OFB} is the total bundle area.
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32 *2.4. Solar luminaires*

33 The effective utilization of natural light inside buildings depends on the
34 solar luminaires. A solar luminaire is an optical element designed to diffuse
35 light with a uniform illuminance level at the working plane. A solar luminaire
36 has to minimize transmission losses and glare, and maximize the utilization
37 of available light [36]. There are two types of solar luminaires: passive and
38 hybrid. Hybrid solar luminaires, besides distributing direct sunlight, are
39 equipped with electric lamps. A solar luminaire is made of materials such as
40 purified silica glass or a synthetic polymer called Poly(methyl methacrylate)
41 or PMMA. The efficiency of a solar luminaire, η_{SL} , can be around 80% [37].
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46 *2.5. Lighting control system*

47 Hybrid solar luminaires are equipped with dimmable electric lamps and a
48 photocell that supplement natural light in order to compensate the fluctua-
49 tions in the intensity of collected sunlight [38]. These fluctuations are caused
50 by changing cloud coverage or solar collector movement. A good lighting
51 control must quickly compensate these fluctuations keeping a constant il-
52 luminance level [39]. In this work the lighting control system will not be
53 studied.
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3. Design of the SSLFR

The calculation of the Sun position is required in order to determine the annual output of the daylighting system. The Sun position can be calculated using an implementation of the Solpos algorithm [40]. This algorithm calculates, as a function of location and local time, the solar angles: height angle of the sun (α_S), zenith angle of the sun (θ_z), and azimuth of the sun (γ_S). These angles are needed to calculate the angle of incidence of solar radiation. Considering a SSLFR aligned horizontally and aligned in a North-South orientation, the angle of incidence of solar radiation will be calculated in two projection planes: the transversal incidence angle (θ_t) and the longitudinal incidence angle (θ_l) [41]. These angles are related to the transversal and longitudinal study, respectively. The transversal incidence angle (θ_t) is defined as the angle between the vertical and the projection of the sun vector on the East-West plane (the plane orthogonal to the mirror width), and the longitudinal incidence angle (θ_l) is defined as the angle between the vertical and the projection of the sun vector on the North-South plane.

Fig. 3. Parameters used in transversal study.

3.1. Parameters used in the transversal design

The basic parameters used in the transversal study are as follows: mirror width (W_M), vertical distance between the OFB and the mirrors (f), separation between two consecutive mirrors (d), aperture of the right trapezium (B), and number of mirrors at each side of the central mirror (n) (the total number of mirrors of the SSLFR is $2n + 1$). From these parameters we can determine the angle between the vertical at the focal point and the line connecting the centre point of each mirror to the focal point (α_i), and the width

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9 illuminated on the aperture of the reflector cavity by the i -th mirror (W_{ai}).
10 Fig. 3 shows the parameters used in the transversal study.

11 The angle between the vertical at the focal point and the line connecting
12 the centre point of each mirror to the focal point (α_i) is given by:
13

$$14 \quad \alpha_i = \arctan \left[\frac{i \cdot (W_M + d) - B/2}{f} \right]; \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (6)$$

15 The maximum value of this angle has to be smaller than the acceptance
16 angle of the individual optical fibre:
17

$$18 \quad \alpha_n \leq \theta_c \quad (7)$$

19 Therefore,

$$20 \quad \arctan \left[\frac{n \cdot (W_M + d) - B/2}{f} \right] \leq \theta_c \quad (8)$$

21 The parameters that most influence the design of a SSLFR are W_M and
22 f . The value of d is determined by [30], where the authors used a method
23 inspired by what is known as ‘Mathur’s method’ ([42], [43]), which calculates
24 the appropriate value of the shift between adjacent mirrors such that shading
25 and blocking of reflected rays are avoided. The mirror width is then given
26 by:
27

$$28 \quad W_M \leq \frac{f \tan \theta_c + B/2}{n} - d \quad (9)$$

29 Applying ‘Mathur’s method’, the relationship between W_M and d is as
30 follows:
31

$$32 \quad d \geq 0.075 \cdot W_M \quad (10)$$

33 The typical values of the numerical aperture of an individual fiber are
34 between 0.39 and 0.6 (see [45]). Fig. 4 shows the relationship between W_M ,
35 NA , and f , for $n = 12$. For the same value of f , if the fiber has a smaller NA ,
36 W_M must be smaller. For the same value of NA , if f is larger, W_M may be
37 larger. However, increasing f also induces competing effects, such as focusing
38 accuracy losses, which tend to reduce the collector optical efficiency.
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Fig. 4. Relationship between W_M , NA , and f .

Fig. 5 shows the relationship between W_M , NA , and n , for $f = 1.5$ m. For the same value of n , if the fiber has a smaller NA , W_M must be smaller. For the same value of NA , if n is smaller, W_M may be larger. Also, a smaller n allows to decrease the cost of the SSLFR.

Fig. 5. Relationship between W_M , NA , and n .

The width illuminated on the aperture of the reflector cavity by the i -th mirror (W_{ai}) can be calculated as:

$$W_{ai} = W_M \cdot [\cos \beta_i \pm \sin \beta_i \cdot \tan \alpha_i]; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (11)$$

where β_i is the tilt of the i -th mirror for $0 \leq i \leq 2n$. The sign \pm must be adopted according to the following criteria: $-$ for the left side, and $+$ for the right side. The tilt of the central mirror (β_0) is given by:

$$\beta_0 = \frac{-\theta_t}{2} \quad (12)$$

where θ_t is the transversal incidence angle (see [41]). The tilt on the left side (β_i^l) is given by:

$$\beta_i^l = \frac{-\theta_t - \alpha_i}{2}; 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (13)$$

while the tilt on the right side (β_i^r) is given by:

$$\beta_i^r = \frac{-\theta_t + \alpha_i}{2}; 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (14)$$

Finally, the position of each mirror with respect to the central mirror (L_i) can be calculated as:

$$L_i = i \cdot (W_M + d); 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (15)$$

3.2. Parameters used in the longitudinal design

The basic parameters used in the longitudinal study are as follows: angle between the mirror axis and the horizontal plane (β_M), angle between the *OFB* and the horizontal plane (β_{OFB}), zenithal solar angle (θ_z), mirror length (L_M), and total length of the *OFB* (L_{OFB}). Fig. 6 shows the parameters used in the longitudinal study.

Fig. 6. Parameters used in longitudinal study.

Due to longitudinal symmetry, we only need to take into account the central mirror for this study. After some computations, we have:

$$x_0 = \frac{\left[f + \frac{L_M}{2} [\sin \beta_M - \cos \beta_M \tan \beta_{OFB}] \right] \tan \mu}{1 + \tan \beta_{OFB} \tan \mu} \quad (16)$$

and

$$x_f = \frac{\left[f + \frac{L_M}{2} [\cos \beta_M \tan \beta_{OFB} - \sin \beta_M] \right] \tan \mu}{1 + \tan \beta_{OFB} \tan \mu} \quad (17)$$

We thus define the left illuminated length of the *OFB* (l_{OFB}^l) as:

$$l_{OFB}^l = \frac{x_0 + \frac{L_M}{2} \cos \beta_M}{\cos \beta_{OFB}} \quad (18)$$

and the right illuminated length of the *OFB* (l_{OFB}^r) as:

$$l_{OFB}^r = \frac{\frac{L_M}{2} \cos \beta_M - x_f}{\cos \beta_{OFB}} \quad (19)$$

With the sign convention that we have adopted, lengths from the centre of the mirror to the left are considered positive, and those to the right negative. The total illuminated length of the *OFB* (l_{OFB}) is equal to:

$$l_{OFB} = l_{OFB}^l - l_{OFB}^r \quad (20)$$

The angles β_M and β_{OFB} can take different values, and the mirrors and the *OFB* can have lateral movement or not. In this study, we have chosen two different configurations: C_1 , without lateral movement; and C_2 , with lateral movement of the mirrors and the *OFB*. C_1 is the configuration used in large-scale LFRs, where the mirrors and the *OFB* form an angle of 0° with the horizontal plane. In configuration C_2 , the rays reflected by the mirrors in the longitudinal direction are always vertical for any time of the day, varying the angle of incidence on the *OFB*. Among all the possible configurations and using the same dimensional parameters, C_2 projects the greatest amount of luminous energy on the *OFB*. Table 1 shows the main characteristics of both configurations.

Table 1. Configurations object of study.

Configuration	Mirrors		OFB	
	β_M ($^\circ$)	Motion	β_{OFB} ($^\circ$)	Motion
C_1	0	No	0	No
C_2	$\theta_z/2$	Yes	$\theta_z/2$	Yes

The position and length of the *OFB* have been calculated using the method proposed by [31], which allows to obtain the optimal values of the

total length, left length, and right length of the *OFB* (L_{OFB} , L_{OFB}^l , and L_{OFB}^r respectively).

3.3. Design of the reflector cavity

There are several considerations involved in the design of the reflector cavity: optical, thermal, material and cost. The main goals of our design are: firstly, to maximise the optical efficiency of the reflexion of the incident solar irradiance; and secondly, to minimise the bundle packing fraction.

The aperture of the reflector cavity must have a rectangular shape since the primary mirror field illuminates on the secondary concentrator a rectangular surface. Therefore, the reflector cavity proposed consists of two right trapeziums. Fig. 7 shows a schematic diagram of the reflector cavity, where B is the long base, b is the short base, and h is the height, that is, the depth of the air cavity. Each trapezium collects the incident solar irradiance of the mirrors located at each side of the central mirror. The reflector cavity has two focal points, located in the middle of the aperture of each trapezium ($B/2$). The central mirror is, however, focused on the point of attachment of the two right trapeziums.

Thus, the main design variables are:

- i) The size of the aperture of the right trapezium, B .
- ii) The size of the *OFB*, b .
- iii) The depth of the air cavity, h .

The design constraints are as follows:

- i) B must be greater than the maximum hourly value of W_{ai} (see equation 11):

$$B \succ W_{ai \max} \quad (21)$$

ii) b should be as small as possible to decrease the number of optical fibers. However, the smaller b , the greater the possibility that the rays will bounce inside the absorber cavity and exit through the aperture. The choice of the value of b determines the value of the depth of the air cavity.

iii) h depends on the value of b . If b is smaller, h must also be smaller to ensure that all rays impinge on the *OFB*.

A Matlab code was developed in order to trace the Sun's rays inside the reflector cavity. This code calculates all the necessary optical parameters (illuminated width on the *OFB*, incidence angle on the *OFB*, and reflected

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rays out of the reflector cavity), given the values of B , b and h . Fig. 8 shows the Sun's rays reflected by the 10th mirror located on the left.

Fig. 7. Schematic diagram.

Fig 8. Optical simulation.

The preceding study is based on the incident light rays being parallel. Actually, this is not true: because of the finite angular size of the sun's disc, the Sun's rays reaching the OFB are not parallel. Therefore, this consideration affects the design of the reflector cavity. It specifically affects the calculation of the aperture of the reflector cavity. Let us consider the angular diameter of the sun's disc, $\xi \simeq 9.3$ mrad (see Shanmugapriya et al. [46]). Fig. 9 shows that taking this parameter into consideration means that the focus width, W_{an} , varies with respect to the value calculated in (11 with $i = n$). The illuminated area is now increased in two values that we shall call d'_n and d''_n . Their values affect the aperture of the reflector cavity.

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Fig. 9. Reflection of non-parallel rays.

The aim is thus to calculate the length of the lower leg of the striped, right-angled triangles in Fig. 7. To determine these distances, we straightforwardly have that:

$$H'_n = [L_n^2 + f^2]^{1/2} - \left[\left(\frac{W_M}{2} \sin(\beta_n) \right)^2 + \left(\frac{W_M}{2} \cos(\beta_n) - \frac{W_M}{2} [\cos(\beta_n) \pm \sin(\beta_n) \tan(\alpha_n)] \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (22)$$

$$H''_n = [L_n^2 + f^2]^{1/2} + \left[\left(\frac{W_M}{2} \sin(\beta_n) \right)^2 + \left(\frac{W_M}{2} \cos(\beta_n) - \frac{W_M}{2} [\cos(\beta_n) \pm \sin(\beta_n) \tan(\alpha_n)] \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (23)$$

The sign \pm must be adopted, once again, according to the following criteria: $-$ for the left side, and $+$ for the right side. Hence, the distances to determine are:

$$d'_n = H'_n \tan \frac{\xi}{2} \quad (24)$$

$$d''_n = H''_n \tan \frac{\xi}{2} \quad (25)$$

These values of d'_n and d''_n are then added to the previously calculated value of W_{an} .

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9 *3.4. Luminous flux of the daylighting system*

10 The output luminous flux, Φ_{out} , can be calculated by the following ex-
11 pression:
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$$13 \quad \Phi_{out} = K_b \cdot T(\lambda) \cdot \eta_{SL} \cdot Q_{OFB} \quad (26)$$

14 where K_b is the luminous efficacy of the direct radiation (in lm/W), $T(\lambda)$
15 is the transmissivity of the individual optical fibre for a specific wavelength
16 (λ), η_{SL} is the efficiency of the solar luminaire, and Q_{OFB} is input power on
17 the core area of the *OFB* (in W).
18

19 The input power on the aperture of the reflector cavity will be calculated
20 using the equation presented by [31], that it is particularly suitable for the
21 case of working with SSLFRs:
22

$$23 \quad Q = \sum_{i=0}^{2n} DNI \cdot \eta_{opt} \cdot IAF_i \cdot A_{effec\ i} \quad (27)$$

24 where:

25 (i) DNI is the direct normal irradiance.

26 (ii) η_{opt} is the total optical yield, which is calculated considering the re-
27 flectivity of the mirrors (ρ_m), the reflectivity of the reflector cavity (ρ_{rc}), and
28 the cleanliness factors of the mirrors (CI_m) and the *OFB* (CI_{OFB}):
29

$$30 \quad \eta_{opt} = \rho_m \cdot CI_m \cdot CI_{OFB} \cdot \rho_{rv} \quad (28)$$

31 The considered values are: $\rho_m = 0.94$, $\rho_{rv} = 0.94$ (see [47]), and $CI_m =$
32 $CI_{OFB} = 0.96$ (see [44]).

33 (iii) IAF_i considers the variation in the optical performance of a SSLFR
34 for varying ray incidence angles, which is calculated using the equation shown
35 by [30].
36

37 (iv) $A_{effec\ i}$ is the effective area of the aperture of the reflector cavity
38 that is actually illuminated by the i -th mirror. This area can be determined
39 with W_{ai} and l_{OFB} :
40

$$41 \quad A_{effec\ i} = W_{ai} \cdot l_{OFB}; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (29)$$

42 The effective area of the *OFB* that is actually illuminated by the i -th mirror
43 ($A_{effec\ OFB\ i}$) can be determined as:
44

$$45 \quad A_{effec\ OFB\ i} = CR_i \cdot A_{OFB}; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (30)$$

where A_{OFB} is the total *OFB* area, and CR_i is the concentration ratio of the i -th mirror, which is given by:

$$CR_i = \frac{A_{effec\ i}}{A_{OFB}}; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (31)$$

Therefore, the input power on the core area of the OFB, is given by:

$$Q_{OFB} = \sum_{i=0}^{2n} DNI \cdot \eta_{opt} \cdot IAF_i \cdot BPF \cdot CR_i \cdot A_{OFB} \quad (32)$$

From these equations, the output luminous flux (26) is given by:

$$\Phi_{out} = K_b \cdot T(\lambda) \cdot \eta_{SL} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{2n} DNI \cdot \eta_{opt} \cdot IAF_i \cdot BPF \cdot CR_i \cdot A_{OFB} \quad (33)$$

4. Results and discussion

The assumptions made in this study are as follows:

- (i) The mirrors are flat and specularly reflecting.
- (ii) The rows of mirrors are perfectly tracked so as to follow the apparent movement of the Sun.
- (iii) The pivoting point of each mirror coincides with its central point; hence, it is always focused on the focal point of one trapezium of the reflector cavity.

The following parameters remain constant in all the configurations:

- (i) $n = 12$, considered optimal for the design of a SSLFR [30].
- (ii) $W_M = 0.030$ (m), considered optimal for the design of a SSLFR, according to the method proposed by [30].
- (iii) $d = 0.022$ (m). This value was obtained using a method inspired by what is known as ‘Mathur’s method’, which calculates the appropriate value of the shift between adjacent mirrors so that shading and blocking of reflected rays are avoided, for a transversal incidence angle between -22.5° and 22.5° . In any case, the numerical simulations, performed using MATLAB, also take into account the effects of shading and blocking, in those hours in which they exist.
- (iv) $f = 1.5$ (m), considered optimal for the design of a SSLFR [30] and obtained by applying Mathur’s method

(v) $L_M = 2.5$ (m), considered optimal for the design of a SSLFR [30] and obtained by applying Mathur's method.

(vi) Reflector cavity parameters: $B = 0.0364$ (m), $b = 0.01092$ (m), and $h = 0.070$ (m).

(vii) L_{OFB} , L_{OFB}^l , and L_{OFB}^r , calculated according to Barbon's method [31]. This values are shown in Table 2. With the sign convention that we have adopted, lengths from the centre of the mirror to the left are considered positive, and those to the right, negative. These results were obtained by setting $f = 1.5$ (m) and $L_M = 2.5$ (m).

Table 2. Values of the OFB's position and length.

Configuration	L_{OFB}^l	L_{OFB}^r	L_{OFB}
C_1	0.212	-2.287	2.50
C_2	1.25	-1.25	2.50

(viii) $K_b = 104$ lm/W [29].

(ix) $d_{of} = 0.0014$ (m), taken from manufacturer data ([45]).

(x) $d_c = 0.001$ (m), taken from manufacturer data ([45]).

(xi) $dBloss = 12$ (dB/Km), taken from manufacturer data ([45]).

(xii) $BPF = 40\%$.

(xiii) $\eta_{SL} = 80\%$ [37].

(xiv) $L = 0.010$ (Km).

With these values, α_i is less than the acceptance angle of the individual optical fibre.

The study was conducted in Almeria (Spain), with latitude $36^\circ 50' 07'' N$, longitude $02^\circ 24' 08'' W$ and altitude 22 m. These calculations were developed by using ground-based irradiance measurement data collected at the Andalusian Energy Agency (AAE) [48]. The mathematical equations were implemented in a MATLAB code which includes subroutines, discretized every 10 minutes, to calculate: DNI , mirror position, IAF , W_{ai} , and l_{OFB} . The program takes into account the effects of shading, blocking and end loss.

4.1. Output luminous flux

Fig. 10 shows the calculation of the output luminous energy per month, for both configurations C_1 and C_2 . As can be seen in this figure, configuration C_2 gives better results than configuration C_1 .

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Fig. 10. The luminous energy computed for month.

4.2. Electric energy saving: a case study

A typical office room has been considered in order to evaluate the electric energy saving of the daylighting system. Electric lighting is a major energy consumer in offices [49]. The interior of an office room is organized around the needs of individual workstations which are typically 3 m x 3 m [50]. In this study, an office for 8 individual workstations is considered. The office characteristics are summarized in Table 3. The lighting system consists of a combination of daylight and electric light. Supplementary electric lighting is not used if the daylight system provides more than 500 lx of average illumination level. The electric lighting system is controlled by light sensors. The rated values of the lamps, taken from the manufacturer's catalog, are summarized in Table 4. The utilisation factor of the luminaires is assumed to be 0.44, and the luminous flux delivered was calculated using the lumen method. The number of lamps is 32 and the total electric consumption is 576 W.

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Table 3. Data from the office object of study.

Data	Value
Office dimension (L x W x H)	12 m x 6 m x 3 m
Office reflectance ($\rho_{ceiling}$ x ρ_{wall} x ρ_{floor})	0.5 x 0.5 x 0.2
Other object reflectance	1.0
Height of working plane from floor	0.85 m
Maintenance factor	0.8
Average illumination level [51]	500 lx
Office working hours	09:00 to 16:30

Table 4. Rated values of comercial lamps [52].

Lamp type	Wattage (W)	Lumens	Rated life (h)
Fluorescent lamp (FL)	18	1350	20000

The electric saving is estimated calculating the electric consumption of the combined system every 10 min, and comparing this value with the electric consumption without the daylighting system. The electric consumption of the SSLFR was ignored in this study, since it is very small compared to the total electric consumption. Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 show, in percentage terms, the electric saving for both configurations C_1 and C_2 , computed on June 21st (Summer solstice) and December 21st (Winter solstice). For the worst day of the year, with configuration C_1 , the energy saving is higher than 20 % during 5 hour. On June 21st, the energy saving with configuration C_1 is higher than 50 % during office working hours. For the worst day of the year, with C_2 configuration, the energy saving is higher than 30% during 5 hours. On June 21st, the energy saving with configuration C_2 is higher than 70 % during 5 hours. It is clear that configuration C_2 gives higher electric savings.

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Fig. 11. The percentage electric saving computed for C_1 configuration.

Fig. 12. The percentage electric saving computed for C_2 configuration.

5. Conclusions and future perspectives

In this study, aspects of the design of a small scale linear Fresnel reflector applied to a daylighting system based on optical fiber bundles were analyzed.

This study shows the influence of the numerical aperture of the optical fiber on the parameters of the *SSLFR*: mirror width, number of mirrors at each side of the central mirror, and distance between the OFB and the mirrors. The use of optical fibers with small numerical aperture requires a smaller mirror width. The mirror width can be increased by increasing

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9 the distance between the mirrors and the optical fiber, but this solution is
10 not recommended as it tends to reduce the optical efficiency of the collector.
11 The mirror width can also be increased by decreasing the mirror number,
12 which would decrease the cost of the *SSLFR*. It was found that the Barbon
13 method is suitable to determine the length and position of the *OFB*. This
14 paper addresses also the preliminary design of a new reflector cavity for
15 the *SSLFR*. This reflector cavity has two focal points, which increases the
16 number of solar rays that impinge on the *OFB*. Optical simulations have been
17 performed in order to to evaluate the optical efficiency of the reflector cavity
18 proposed. Two configurations of the *SSLFR*, C_1 and C_2 , were analyzed and
19 the electric energy savings were evaluated. Future work will entail the study
20 of the use of this daylighting system in applications such as formulti-floor
21 office buildings, underground stations, etc.
22

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